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Article

Green Business & Consumerism

Sandeep Saxena

Assistant Professor
School of Commerce & Management, India
Email: sandeep.saxena@rnbglobal.edu.in

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ABSTRACT

In today's market, the choice for consumers has increased manifold with increase in the range of models that is why the businesses also has started on focusing on different scenario. Under such circumstances, choosing an appropriate product that suits one's value propositions is the most important. Today's marketplace is motivated by the importance of the "Green consumerism" and will become even more responsive to products and services promising environmental responsibility. So many of the firms has started the 'Green Business Strategy' by manufacturing & promoting the eco-friendly products like in cosmetics & edible products use of aloovira, avoiding the different chemicals etc. which can harm to the individual as well as society. Consumers are now concerned more than ever about the environmental impact of products they buy. As a result, the number of industries under fire from environmentalists has grown very rapidly. Green consumerism has helped to spur significant shifts in the way in which some industries view the environmental challenge. Terms such as 'recyclable, biodegradable, eco-friendly, sustainable, computable and bio-based' are the latest Key words which green consumers looks for when they buy products. The broad scope of these Key words suggests that green consumers scrutinize products at every phase of product/service life cycle, from raw material procurement, manufacturing and production straight through to product reuse, repair, recycling and eventual disposal, While in use attributes continue to be of primary importance, environmental shopping agenda now increasingly encompass factors that consumers can not feel or see. Consumers desire to know how raw materials are procured and where from they come, how food is processed, what are the resources utilized to produce that particular product and what are their potential impacts on the environment once they land in the trash box? An attempt is therefore made to share some of the experiences on the ethics based consumerism in Indian perspective.

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1. Introduction

Ethical consumerism should be about using our purchasing power to make the world a better place & the best way to recycle in eco-friendly manner. Feeling pure will not help the world's poor.
Julian Baggini

1. What is ethical consumerism?

Ethical consumerism is concerned with how you spend your money and the products you purchase.

- Is it true that what you spend your money on has an impact on others and the environment?
- Ethical customers purchase goods from ethical businesses that attempt not to harm the environment or society.
- Our consumption has an impact on the environment as well.
- Does our wealth and happiness come at the expense of others?

In today's market, consumers' options have multiplied as the number of models available has

grown. Choosing an acceptable product that meets one's value propositions becomes all the more critical in such scenarios. There's no disputing that making a decision has become a crucial duty for a buyer, but it doesn't always end there. They want to know a few more details before or after purchasing a product. The advent of the "Green Consumer" or "Environmentalism" is driving today's marketplace, which will grow even more attentive to products and services that promise environmental responsibility long into the twenty-first century.

Consumers nowadays are more concerned than ever before about the environmental impact of the things they purchase. Consumers who are pragmatic buy products and packages that can be recycled or disposed of responsibly in their areas. As a result, the number of industries targeted by environmentalists has increased dramatically. Green Consumerism has influenced substantial changes in how some companies see the environmental challenge.

Green consumers are driven by universal demands, even if they express their environmental concerns in unique ways. (See table 1) These demands result in new purchasing techniques, which have ramifications for product development and marketing.

Table-1
Green market consumer psychology and purchasing methods

NEEDS		STRATEGIES
Information	----->	Read labels
Control	----->	Take preventive measures
Make a difference	----->	Switch brands
Maintain lifestyles	----->	Buy interchangeable alternatives

Source: J. Ottman Consulting, Inc.

Green shoppers are increasingly looking for terms like "recyclable," "environmentally friendly," "sustainable," "computable," and "bio-based" when purchasing products. Green consumers analyse products at every stage of their life cycle, from raw material acquisition, manufacture, and production

through product reuse, repair, recycling, and eventual disposal, according to the broad scope of these Key phrases (Refer table II). While in-use features remain the most important consideration, environmental buying agendas are increasingly including factors that consumers cannot feel or see. They want to know how

and where raw materials are obtained, how food is grown, and what influence they may have on the environment until they reach the scrap bin.

**TABLE – II
GREEN PURCHASING KEY WORDS**

Raw Materials	Manufacturing	Packaging	Distribution
Sustainable-harvested Petroleum-Free plant-based	Non- Polluting unbleached pesticide- free	Recycled Non-aerosol Source-reduced	Energy-efficient Reusable- packaging

Marketing	In-use	After use
Ethical Informative Cause –related	Low fume Resource – efficient Durable	Recyclable Refillable Reusable

Manufacturer
Socially - Responsible

Source: J. Ottman Consulting, Inc.

Companies have moved their efforts from traditional marketing to "Green Marketing" as a result of this customer transformation. In fact, some academics have gone so far as to profile green product customers in order to understand their demographic composition and market behaviour, and then sell items based on their preferences. Environmental marketing is more difficult to understand than traditional marketing. It accomplishes two main goals:

- To create items with a low environmental impact and that are both convenient and environmentally friendly.
- Environmental sensitivity, taking into account both the product's features and the company's environmental track record.

Consumers are no longer seen as people with a voracious need for material items, but as human beings worried about the state of the planet around them, according to successful green marketers. Green

marketing is best practised by companies who are proactive in their approach. These organisations see themselves as intertwined with the natural world's processes. Outside, they form cooperative, positive partnerships with environmental stakeholders, and they collaborate with suppliers and retailers to handle environmental challenges along the value chain. Internally, cross-functional teams get together to identify the most holistic solutions to environmental problems. These businesses are primarily focused on the long term rather than the short term, with the goal of not only making a profit but also contributing to society through a socio-cause-related marketing strategy.

Despite the fact that many companies have begun to take this strategy, I'd like to mention a few other elements that may help to shed light on factors affecting ethical consumerism:

- Veal production has also been criticised, as many people believe it is inhumane.

Slavery:

- Millions of people are enslaved all over the world.
- People are bought and sold, and forced to labour for little or no compensation, in horrific working conditions with no way to protect themselves from mistreatment.
- Despite the fact that it is illegal, some people are brought to the UK and forced to work against their will, typically because they are afraid of being detected by the authorities.
- Would you purchase a product if you knew it was made by slaves?

Child-Labour:

- In many places of the world, children are forced to work. They are sometimes compelled to do so by kinds of slavery, but acute poverty forces children to work in order to survive. They are deprived of an education and the upbringing that we in the West are accustomed to.
- Would you buy anything if you knew it was manufactured with child labour?
- Would you buy things created by youngsters under the age of 18 if you were on vacation in a foreign country?

Animal welfare:

- Many people no longer tolerate the thought of mistreating animals because it is evident that they suffer in the same way that humans do.
- Modern agricultural methods include confining a large number of animals in small spaces, allowing them limited movement, and feeding them manufactured food. This is done to save money, yet it may result in animal suffering. Concerns have recently been raised about the transportation of animals in lorries across great distances.

Free range eggs:

Free range eggs and barn eggs are sold alongside regular eggs in supermarkets. Battery-caged chickens lay more eggs than free-range chickens. This is not stated on the label.

The chickens are kept in little wire cages with access to food and water. They spend the majority of their lives in this place solely to lay eggs.

Free range and barn eggs are produced by birds who live in more natural settings. They are not restricted, and they are free to roam and consume their regular food.

Would you prefer free range or non-free range eggs?

Would you be willing to pay more for free range eggs if they were more expensive?

Fur:

Fur coats were once considered a high-end fashion item worn by rich women. Fur isn't as popular as it once was, and that's not only because of the price. Several pressure groups have worked to raise public awareness about the brutality of fur manufacture.

People who have worn fur in public have received a lot of criticism.

Is wearing a fur coat appropriate or inappropriate? What about the material leather?

Which would you choose if you had to choose between a genuine fur coat and a faux fur coat?

Ethical banking & investment:

Your money is invested by the bank in order to create a profit. It pays you some of the profit as

interest. How would you feel if you learned that your bank had put your money into:

- The armaments trade with developing countries, which aided in the continuation of violence.
- Aiding and abetting corrupt governments and regimes
- Exploitation and cruelty to animals?

Some banks offer investments that ensure your money isn't wasted on these things.

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